

1 **A new criterion for Multi-purpose platforms siting: fish endurance to wave motion**
2 **within offshore farming cages**

3 Giulio Brizzi* and Maroua Sabbagh*

4 *Chlamys s.r.l., Via S. Gervasio, 80 - 76125 Trani (BT) - Italy

5 E-mail: gbrizzi@chlamys.it; maroua.sabbagh@gmail.com

6

7 **Abstract**

8 Early studies have described the existence of a critical speed in fish when challenged by
9 unidirectional currents, often calculated as number of body length/second (BL/sec). In
10 salmon farming, the criterion related to the disruption of normal swimming behaviour in cage
11 and the consequent onset of intense aerobic challenging, marked by the start of ram
12 ventilation, has recently been proposed with regard to unidirectional currents under tidal
13 conditions. Unfortunately, this criterion appears only partially satisfactory within the
14 specificity of the marine offshore environment, where wave motion dominates even at
15 relevant depth, as in the case of long-lasting storms and associated waves in long wavelength,
16 not uncommonly over 100 m of length.

17 In the present work, the orbital velocities generated by wave motion at different depths are
18 proposed as additional criteria, besides critical speeds to unidirectional currents, to define the
19 likely limits of exposure of fish stocks farmed in offshore environments and consequently, to
20 set up a range of sea states compatible with fish welfare. This finding can support the
21 definition of an acceptable sea state for the whole Multi-Purpose Platform (MPP) design,
22 where the farmed fish are considered as the weakest link in the platform chain design.

23 **Keywords**

24 Multi-purpose offshore platform, Fish endurance, Wave motion, Offshore aquaculture, The
25 Blue Growth Farm.

26 **Highlights**

27 Fish endurance to wave motion in offshore cages

28 Criteria for MPP siting

29 Fish welfare in offshore cages

30 **Introduction**

31 The onset of a new generation of Multi-purpose Platforms (MPPs) designed to operate in the
32 open sea and combining wave and wind energy extracting devices with huge water volumes
33 devoted to fish farming, has led to an unexpected technological challenge - the coupling of
34 infrastructure for high energy sites with profitable fish culture units. Engineering Standards
35 and Codes from the existing offshore industry provide references for platform design,
36 validated to cope with all the expected sea states at the final installation site, although the
37 association of living and mobile organisms with high-energy environments is not obvious.

38 Some authors (Zanuttigh et al., 2016), within the frame of the past EU FP7 project, have
39 described a method to identify the best design solution for MPPs, including the technological
40 features of either single- or multi-use platforms, to be selected for a given site. This method
41 proposes a pre-screening phase, where the basic questions on the site potential are addressed,
42 and a ranking phase where a value is associated to each envisaged technological solution.
43 Although substantially based on engineering concepts, the method does not refer to any
44 relationship between sea states and fishes' ability to withstand energetic environments.

45 A number of methods have been applied to the study of swimming speed performance in
46 fishes, from short-term intense current exposure trials to testing of maximum critical speed in
47 incremental steps, up to trials evaluating fish long-term endurance to a fixed speed. Brett
48 (1964) first developed the original concept of the critical swimming speed (U_{crit}), based on
49 the measure of the swimming fish performance under increasing flow speeds. The U_{crit} values
50 were correlated (Farlinger & Beamish, 1977; Williams & Brett, 1987) with the current
51 velocity and trial duration. U_{crit} estimations correlated with maximum prolonged swimming
52 speed were provided by Wilson & Egginton (1994), Hammer (1995) and Plaut (2001).
53 Several authors (Jones et al., 1974; Hartwell & Otto, 1991; Kolok, 1991; Hawkins & Quinn,
54 1996; Lowe, 1996; Myrick & Cech, 2000; Fisher, 2005) have used the U_{crit} of different fish
55 species to investigate the correlation between fishes' swimming capabilities, their biological
56 characteristics and the fundamental ecological variables, such as the local hydraulic
57 environment. Videler (1993) demonstrated that prolonged swimming performance over daily
58 times scales are of major importance in foraging activity and habitat exploitation in fish. The
59 relationship between certain important ecological fish traits such as routine field speed and
60 critical swimming speed was investigated by Plaut (2000), and Fisher & Bellwood (2003);
61 the sustained speed and sprint speeds have also been investigated in a small number of fish
62 taxa by Brett (1964), Fisher & Wilson (2004) and Reidy et al. (2000). Plaut (2001),
63 considering the relevance of fish speeds to the fish biology and ecology, concluded that the
64 U_{crit} represents a reliable measure of fish swimming speed capability.

65 Several swimming tunnel studies have reported the U_{crit} in salmonids. In adult reared Atlantic
66 salmon (*Salmo salar*) the attained U_{crit} (weight 1.75 kg, fork length (L_f) = 51.3 cm, at 14°C)
67 was 100 cm/sec (Remen et al., 2016). In adult wild *S. salar* (L_f = 55–60 cm) U_{crit} ranged
68 between 176 cm/sec and 216 cm/sec at respectively 13°C and 18°C (Booth et al., 1997;
69 Thorstad et al., 2008). Remen et al. (2016) demonstrated that U_{crit} value shifts with size from

70 80.6 cm/sec in small post-smolts of approximately 80 g to 90.9 cm/sec in larger post-smolts
71 (≈ 289 g) and 99.5 cm/sec in adults (≈ 1750 g). U_{crit} , when expressed as BL/sec, is inversely
72 correlated with fork lengths, i.e. it is higher in smaller fish. In a push-cage experiment on
73 reared specimens, the attained U_{crit} was 125 cm/sec (3.4 kg, $L_f = 63$ cm, 7-7.5°C, Hvas et al.,
74 2017).

75 Basaran et al. (2007) studied the swimming performances of Gilthead seabream (*Sparus*
76 *aurata*) in a current channel. Absolute U_{crit} performance, in wild and farmed fish, showed an
77 increase with the fish length and the average U_{crit} of wild fish of wild was higher (0.86 m/sec)
78 in a significant way compared to farmed fish (0.79 m/sec). The relative U_{crit} was also
79 negatively correlated with the fish length (Figure 1) and significantly higher in wild fish (4.52
80 BL/sec) compared to farmed ones (4.21 BL/sec).

81 Seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) U_{crit} was observed in a few studies. Carbonara et al. (2006)
82 observed that U_{crit} , measured in tunnel, was lower than in seabream. The absolute U_{crit}
83 ranged from 0.97 to 1.27 m/sec and relative U_{crit} ranged from 3.6 to 4.1 BL/sec. Different
84 values were reported in the study of Luna-Acosta et al. (2011), ranging from 2.4 to 2.7
85 BL/sec, as standard length.

86 Remen et al. (2016) proposed marking the water velocity thresholds that indicate the safe
87 welfare for salmon farming under exposed conditions, by using the U_{crit} as the limiting value.
88 Beyond that value, a prolonged exposure would lead to physiological depletion, where the
89 fish would no longer be able to move away from the rear closing grid in the experimental
90 tunnel (Wood, 1991).

91 Recently Johansson et al. (2014) and Hvas et al. (2017), studied both endurance and
92 swimming behaviour of Atlantic salmon in offshore cages at different current speeds. Below
93 a current threshold of 20 cm/sec outside the cages (Johansson et al., 2007), *S. salar*

94 maintained a swimming velocity independent from the current velocity outside the cage, and
95 fish moved in circular schools swimming at speeds ranging from 0.3 to 1.1 BL/sec (Dempster
96 et al., 2009; Stien et al., 2016).

97 On a commercial salmon farm in exposed conditions, at the increase in current speed from 20
98 cm/sec to 35 cm/sec and then to velocities over 47 cm/sec, the fish swimming pattern shifted
99 from a circular ranging to a composition of circular movements with a part of the school
100 facing the current, to end in a complete standing against the current of the entire school
101 (Johannson et al., 2014). Swimming behaviour was as shown in Figure 2. At low current
102 velocities the fish swam in a circle (Figure 2-A) and were distributed within the most of the
103 cage volume. The authors assumed this normal schooling structure as marking the
104 preferential fish velocity. At increasing current velocities, part of the school moved to face
105 the current close to the net, while the rest of the school kept circling in an elliptic shape
106 behind them (Figure 2-B). Fish swimming in circle maintained their behaviour up to the
107 exposure of specimens' sides to the vivid current, when they gained a new position by
108 drifting to the sheltered opposite side of the cage. With high current velocity, the circling
109 pattern was completely disrupted and all fish appeared to swim in a dense group facing the
110 current, abandoning the circling swimming pattern (Figure 2-C). After the disruption of
111 circular swimming behaviour, the fish were therefore forced to swim at velocities imposed by
112 the environmental energy acting inside the sea cages. Swimming in the wake of others
113 against the current in a group has been reported to save energy (Herskin et al., 1998), in an
114 attempt to optimize energetic consumption after current speed increase. The same swimming
115 pattern was confirmed in the study of Hvas et al. (2017), where adult salmon in an offshore
116 cage were exposed to strong currents. At flow speed ≈ 65 cm/sec, the onset of the ram
117 ventilation was noticed, to become the dominating respiratory mode in the majority of fish
118 above 100 cm/sec. In the presence of a prolonged swimming activity, ram ventilation thus

119 represents an effective adaptation to higher oxygen requirements. As a consequence,
120 swimming at sustained speeds causing a prolonged ram ventilation would physiologically
121 challenge fish and possibly impair their growth (Hvas et al., 2017). In the wild, Blanchet et
122 al. (2008) reported that the growth of Atlantic salmon was improved by the lower swimming
123 costs sustained at low flow velocities, when compared to swimming costs at intermediate
124 flow speeds. In farming practice, *S. salar* post-smolts grew at significantly higher rates at a
125 current of 0.8 BL/sec compared to 1.5 BL/sec (Solstorm et al., 2015).

126 Wave motion is considered to be one of the most powerful structuring forces in marine
127 communities, and extreme wave events have been reported to cause mass fish stranding
128 (Follet, 1970). Bodkin et al. (1987) reported a mass mortality of kelp-forest associated fish
129 community, after a series of extreme events due to waves of high amplitude and heights of 8–
130 10 m, capable of exceeding the fishes' capacity of maintaining their position. Lassig (1982,
131 1983) reported a large number of fish wounded after a tropical cyclone, likely caused by
132 substratum abrasion, and also a displacement of a number of individuals from their usual
133 habitats. At the same time, Cheal et al. (2002) argued that the majority of fish populations is
134 either able to encompass the effects of these short-lasting wave extremes, or quickly
135 recolonize habitats from sheltered locations after intense wave disturbances. In some cases,
136 extreme wave events can completely remove individuals from their habitats and hence wave
137 disturbance is able to modify the composition and diversity of local fish communities
138 (Connell, 1997; Hughes & Connell, 1999). Jordaan (2010) found that fish community
139 composition was correlated with exposure to waves along the coast of Maine, reflecting a
140 combination of physical factors and physiological barriers.

141 In freshwaters (Gabel et al., 2011), waves can provide an advantage to predatory fish with
142 body shapes adapted to extreme hydraulic environments. The increase of swimming activity

143 recorded in breams was also interpreted as a manoeuvre to escape the wave exposed area.
144 Weihs (1993) reported that posture stability is directly correlated with fish swimming
145 velocity and fish of substantial body sizes have the chance of a larger momentum when
146 caught by waves (Webb, 2002). Stoll and Fischer (2010) found juvenile cyprinids with
147 increased metabolic rates and reduced somatic growth, suggesting a larger energy allocation
148 to swimming activity in the presence of an intense wave action. Moreover, benthic prey
149 availability was related to orbital velocity. Fischer & Eckmann (1997) reported that breams
150 moved from the shallow littoral zone to deeper bottoms when their shape shifted to deep-
151 bodied.

152 Wave energy is also affecting the fish community of coral and rocky reefs (Ebeling & Hixon,
153 1991). Fulton et al. (2001) found a significant correlation between the swimming
154 performance and the distribution and abundance at different wave exposure of labrid fishes
155 (Bellwood & Wainwright, 2001). Fulton & Bellwood (2004) correlated the distribution of
156 temperate labrids at different wave exposures and their swimming performances. Reef fishes'
157 distribution patterns varied within different wave exposures and was correlated with the fish
158 swimming capabilities (Fulton, 2005).

159 Early authors (Blake, 1983; Webb, 1984; Weihs, 1989), demonstrated how the body fish
160 shape is an indicator of swimming capabilities, where fusiform shapes are favoured in fast
161 continuous swimming, and laterally compressed shapes are associated with stability and
162 manoeuvrability at low speeds. Environmental flow velocity has a direct linear relationship
163 with the swimming speed performances of fishes in nearby communities. Fulton (2005)
164 reported how chaetodontiform and subcarangiform body shapes of reef fishes were either
165 completely absent or in low abundance in reef flat habitats swept by the most intense waves
166 and where water flow speeds were close to the upper limit swimming speed of these fish

167 groups. Denny & Gaylord (2002) measured the wave-induced water velocities within rocky
168 intertidal habitats, up to speeds of 2.5 m/sec, and argued that the energy demand for living in
169 such habitats imposes a substantial physical challenge on marine organisms.

170 Sites selected for aquaculture installations in offshore areas are often associated with a
171 relevant wave energy and intense water currents, compared to coastal locations selected for
172 fish farming; several papers (Castro et al., 2013; Davidson, 1997; Gallagher et al., 2001;
173 Huntingford, 2010; Palstra et al., 2015; Palstra & Planas, 2011; Solstorm et al., 2015)
174 explored how fish farmed in offshore cages would physiologically react in exposed
175 environments in terms of growth, stress levels, behaviour and welfare. Wave motions,
176 currents and platform motions can interact with fish living in a confined environment, like the
177 water volume inside a cage net, whose walls and bottom prevent fish from fleeing away to
178 reach a suitable environment, from the point of view of their energetic expenditure and
179 endurance capability. Hence, the exposure of large fish batches to intense wave motion and
180 its possible influence on fish welfare (Ashley, 2007; FEAP Code of Conduct, 2008; Segner et
181 al., 2019) should not be neglected during processes of MPP design and appropriate
182 installation site assessment.

183 The objective of the present study is therefore to establish a design criterion for offshore
184 farming facilities that encompasses the fish capability of coping with harsh hydraulic
185 conditions, within an acceptable welfare. With this aim, the similarity between fish endurance
186 in unidirectional currents and that under the orbital movements generated by storm waves
187 will be discussed, and the rationale behind the fish welfare status related to U_{crit} and the
188 welfare due to wave movements exposition will then be investigated.

189 The three species (seabass, gilthead seabream and Atlantic salmon) suitable for farming
190 within the Blue Growth Farm platform (BGF, www.thebluegrowthfarm.eu) were chosen on

191 the basis of several considerations, including optimal temperature range, value and market
192 share. Only these species are focused on here, as a useful paradigm for establishing a MPP
193 design criterion including fish endurance, although the concept may be widely extended to
194 offshore cage farming. While Atlantic salmon is the most farmed fish species in cold waters,
195 seabass and gilthead seabream well represent Mediterranean fish mariculture; moreover,
196 several other species suitable for offshore aquaculture may be investigated in the future.

197 **Material and methods**

198 To assess a fish sustainable wave motion, the orbital water speed within a wave cycle has
199 been taken into account along the water column, at a step of 1 m, from the surface to the
200 maximum depth where an offshore cage bottom (-35 m) is commonly located.

201 The orbital particle velocity U_{wav} , at increasing depth steps of 1 m, has been calculated based
202 on the formulas in Mosetti (1979).

203 The X and Z semi-axes of the wave particles orbits are:

$$204 \quad X = a (\cosh (2 \pi (z-h) / \lambda) / (\sinh (2 \pi h / \lambda))) \quad (1)$$

$$205 \quad Z = a (\sinh (2 \pi (z-h) / \lambda) / (\sinh (2 \pi h / \lambda))) \quad (2)$$

206 Where:

207 a : wave amplitude, m

208 z : depth where orbit is calculated, m

209 h : bottom depth, m

210 λ : wavelength, m

211 The orbital particle velocity has been derived from the formula for ellipse perimeter

212 calculations, as:

$$213 \quad S = 2 \pi \sqrt{(X^2 + Z^2)/2} \quad (3)$$

214 Representing the distance covered by the water particles within the period T ;

215 Orbital velocity is then obtained as S / T .

$$216 \quad S / T = U_{wav} \quad (4)$$

217 Wave parameters have been calculated using formulas for the JONSWAP spectrum
218 (Hasselmann et al., 1973), as in Boccotti (2004). This spectrum, although not completely
219 fitting the shorter Mediterranean wavelengths (Mosetti, 1979), has been chosen for its general
220 validity.

221 Peak period, T_p , has been calculated as:

$$222 \quad T_p = 8.5 \pi \sqrt{(H_s/4g)} \quad (5)$$

223 Where:

224 H_s is the significant wave, m

225 g the gravity acceleration, m/s^2

226 T_p has then been multiplied by 0.95 to obtain a good estimate of T_s , the significant period,
227 used in further waveform calculations

$$228 \quad T_p * 0.95 = T_s \quad (6)$$

229 The wavelength λ has been calculated from the formula:

$$230 \quad \lambda = (T_s)^2 g / 2\pi \quad (7)$$

231 Under the simplified hypothesis of a sinusoidal wave.

232 Calculations of the orbital velocities at increasing depth, at step of 1 m, were carried out for:

233 *Sea bottom depth*: 100 m; 40 m;

234 *Significant wave H_s* of: 4 m; 5 m; 6 m; 7 m; 8 m;

235 The above values have been assumed as representative of the range of depths commonly
236 exploited by offshore cages and of waves related to severe sea states, possibly representing an
237 operative limit capable of discouraging the farming activities in offshore environments.

238 In Atlantic salmon, Johansson et al. (2014) inferred that a current speed of approximately 0.7
239 BL/sec, indicating the onset of disruption of the voluntary swimming pattern, may be
240 considered the preferential fish speed when free to choose its preferred position in a circling
241 shoal. Keeping the fish a circular structure (with one semi-circle favouring the current and the
242 other against it), they proposed to set at twice this speed (1.4 BL/sec, approximately 0.66
243 U_{crit}) the upper limit of current speed marking the range of water velocities that salmon can
244 withstand without impairing their welfare and growing capability under acceptable farming
245 conditions.

246 The welfare critical speed for salmon U_{welf} , has been here considered as:

247 $0.66 * U_{crit} = U_{welf} \quad (8)$

248 Similarly, the orbital velocity U_{wav} will be considered here as in relationship with the U_{welf} for
249 the same multiplying factor:

250 $0.66 * U_{wav} = U_{welf} \quad (9)$

251 In the present study, the reference wave is the significant wave H_s , defined as the average of
252 the highest third of the waves in a given sea state; commonly considered as the design wave,
253 its value well represents (together with the associated significant period T_s) the mean of the

254 worst part of a storm episode. As it is an average, it does not account for the extreme wave
 255 heights during a storm, of critical importance for fish restrained in cages due to the associated
 256 orbital speeds; the H_s is here chosen as reference value under the assumption that peak waves
 257 have a limited temporal extension, and the U_{welf} setting at 66% of the U_{wav} may ensure a
 258 safety margin to fish endurance.

259 **Results**

260 The criterion established for salmon as the threshold for an acceptable welfare in challenging
 261 hydraulic environments is extended here to seabream and seabass under farming conditions.
 262 In the absence of experimental data on current velocity leading to circling behaviour
 263 disruption for seabass and seabream confined within sea cages, the same value of $0.66 U_{crit}$ is
 264 used here, with the aim of maintaining an acceptable safety margin between their
 265 experimental U_{crit} and the welfare environmental velocity U_{welf} for these species. Following
 266 Basaran et al. (2007) and Carbonara et al. (2006), the U_{welf} values would then be set at 2.7
 267 BL/sec for seabream and 2.5 BL/sec for seabass, considering their average U_{crit} of 4.2 and
 268 3.85 respectively.

269 **Table 1: Proposed values (cm/sec) of sustainable environmental speeds (66% U_{crit} =**
 270 **U_{welf}) for species and size at 20 °C for seabass and seabream, derived from equations in**
 271 **Basaran et al. (2007) and in Carbonara et al. (2006). In salmon for smolt (small and**
 272 **large) at 14°C, and for adult at 7°C, derived from data in Remen et al. (2016) and Hvas**
 273 **et al. (2017)**

Species/size (cm)	5	10	20	30	50	60
Seabream	20	35	55	58		
Seabass	17	32	58	76		

Salmon small smolt		47	53			
Salmon large smolt				59		
Adult salmon					71	77

274

275 While U_{crit} values were experimentally derived in tunnel experiments and for salmon in cages
 276 under an approximately unidirectional current, the recent scientific literature does not report
 277 data on fish endurance under wave movements in a confined environment such as a fish cage.

278 In Table 2, the proposed welfare velocities due to the orbital speeds for some significant
 279 waves are reported. In the calculation, the sea bottom has been set at -100 m, and orbits are
 280 mostly circular down to the cage bottom (-35 m). Safe welfare velocities are attained at
 281 significant depth.

282 **Table 2: Depth of welfare orbital velocity for seabream at various sizes, for significant**
 283 **waves of 4-5-6-7-8 m; sea bottom depth = 100 m**

Seabream size (cm)	5	10	20	30
U_{welf} (m/sec)	0.2	0.35	0.55	0.58
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 4$ m	33 m	25 m	17 m	16 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 5$ m	>35 m	33 m	24 m	23 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 6$ m	>35 m	>35 m	31 m	29 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 7$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 8$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m

284

285 In Table 3, sea bottom has been set to -40 m, thus within half of the wavelength, ranging
 286 from 102 to 204 m. Orbits become quickly elliptical, with the major axis on the X, and safe
 287 depth is deeper than previously. Velocity on the X direction becomes dominant.

288 **Table 3: Depth of welfare orbital velocity for seabream at various sizes, for significant**
 289 **waves of 4-5-6-7-8 m; sea bottom depth = 40 m**

Seabream size (cm)	5	10	20	30
U_{welf} (m/sec)	0.2	0.35	0.55	0.58
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 4$ m	>35 m	25 m	17 m	17 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 5$ m	>35 m	>35 m	25 m	23 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 6$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	34 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 7$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 8$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m

290

291 In Table 4, the different critical speeds for seabass led to a different pattern in safe depths for
 292 each wave compared to seabream, at sea bottom of -100 m. Seabass of 30 cm in length are
 293 safe from 12 m to the cage bottom, with all the wave range up to 8 m H_s in the JONSWAP
 294 spectrum.

295 **Table 4: Depth of welfare orbital velocity for seabass at various sizes, for significant**
 296 **waves of 4-5-6-7-8 m; sea bottom depth = 100 m**

Seabass size (cm)	5	10	20	30
U_{welf} (m/sec)	0.17	0.32	0.58	0.76
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 4$ m,	>35 m	26 m	16 m	12 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 5$ m	>35 m	35 m	23 m	17 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 6$ m	>35 m	>35 m	29 m	29 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 7$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	29 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 8$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	35

297

298 At a sea bottom of -40 m (Table 5), adult seabass (30 cm length) are in safety up to a H_s of 6
 299 m that provides a further 10 m (from -25 to the cage bottom) of safe shelter.

300 **Table 5: Depth of welfare orbital velocity for seabass at various sizes, for significant**
 301 **waves of 4-5-6-7-8 m; sea bottom depth = 40 m**

Seabass size (cm)	5	10	20	30
U_{welf} (m/sec)	0.17	0.32	0.58	0.76
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 4$ m	>35 m	26 m	17 m	12 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 5$ m	>35 m	>35 m	23 m	18 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 6$ m	>35 m	>35 m	34 m	25 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 7$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 8$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m

302

303 Atlantic salmon is able to exploit a relevant part of cage depth under JONSWAP stormy
 304 waves at -100 m (Table 6). At shallower depth (-40 m, Table 7), the cage becomes
 305 unsuitable for adult farming under an acceptable welfare at waves greater than 6 m.

306 **Table 6: Depth of welfare orbital velocity for Atlantic salmon at various sizes, for**
 307 **significant waves of 4-5-6-7-8 m; sea bottom depth = 100 m**

Salmon size (cm)	10	20	30	50	60
U_{welf} (m/sec)	0.47	0.53	0.59	0.71	0.77
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 4$ m	20 m	18 m	16 m	13m	12 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 5$ m	27 m	24 m	22 m	19 m	17 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 6$ m	34 m	31 m	29 m	24 m	22 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 7$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	31 m	28 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 8$ m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	>35 m	35 m

308

309 **Table 7: Depth of welfare orbital velocity for Atlantic salmon at various sizes, for**
310 **significant waves of 4-5-6-7-8 m; sea bottom depth = 40 m**

Salmon size (cm)	10	20	30	50	60
U_{welf} (m/sec)	0.47	0.53	0.59	0.71	0.77
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 4$ m	20 m	18 m	16 m	13 m	12 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 5$ m	28 m	25 m	23 m	19 m	17 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 6$ m	>35 m	>35 m	33 m	27 m	24 m
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 7$ m	>35 m				
U_{welf} depth at $H_s = 8$ m	>35 m				

311

312 Discussion

313 The Blue Growth Farm Project, running under a Horizon 2020 collaborative scheme, aims to
314 design an offshore platform devoted to fish farming, equipped at the same time for a relevant
315 wind and wave energy extraction, and combining different technologies with a high degree of
316 environmental flexibility. During the site selection process, the capability of fish stocks to
317 cope with extreme environmental conditions was raised as a concern, since farmed fish may
318 be considered as the “weakest link” within an offshore platform’s operational chain.

319 Under sea states characterized by long wavelengths (>100 m), the water motion can be
320 relevant even at the depth of the cage bottom, ranging from 10 to 35 m in current offshore
321 aquaculture practice. The water particles’ orbits are at their maximum size at the surface,
322 decreasing exponentially with depth. Therefore, within each wave cycle the fish is forced, in
323 order to maintain its position, to sustain a swimming phase with a total length theoretically
324 approaching the orbit perimeter at the depth where the fish is located, and the duration of

325 movement is close to the wave period, at that depth. It may be argued that a similarity exists
326 between the swimming phases of a circling shoal in a horizontal plane and the corresponding
327 phases generated by the orbital movements of the incoming wave in a vertical plane, both
328 characterized by an active (against current) and a passive phase (with current).

329 The orbital velocity at various depths can generate extreme motion levels, in some cases
330 overcoming fish U_{crit} , particularly within the superficial layers. Here we assume that, within
331 the range of wave motion that a fish is able to withstand without being cast away to collide
332 with the net walls or the cage bottom, the U_{crit} is not attained; at the onset of fish collisions
333 against nettings, the U_{crit} is to be intended as surpassed. During storms, wave periods mostly
334 range from 9 to 15 sec and duration can encompass several hours. Thus, fish may experience
335 a huge number of cycles of swimming (e.g. for a 3 hours peak storm duration at $T = 10$ sec, a
336 number of 1080 cycles is reached), which we assume to be no less energy-consuming than
337 the effort sustained under continuous exercise of rather short duration (from 20 min to 1.5 h
338 in tunnel experiments). As a consequence, the cyclical speed U_{wav} due to orbital motion
339 should not exceed the U_{crit} , and therefore not leading to fish exhaustion under a prolonged
340 storm; to be compatible with an acceptable fish welfare, the U_{welf} is set at 66% of the
341 calculated U_{wav} , as for unidirectional currents (Johansson et al., 2014).

342 Farmed fish ideally take advantage of all of the cage volume within normal farming
343 conditions, and in the event of a stressing episode they may display a schooling behaviour
344 leading to fish grouping in considerable densities, reaching 20 times more than normal
345 (Oppedal et al., 2011). The water column within a farming cage can therefore offer a volume
346 of different thickness depending on incident waves, where fish can stay in a comfortable
347 hydraulic environment. Due to the specific fish U_{crit} at different sizes, this layer can be
348 represented by a significant part of the original cage volume, or be restricted to the deeper
349 cage part, where fish can attain a very high density. The calculations proposed above indicate

350 that, in open marine areas under a severe wave regime, shallow cages may be unsuitable to
351 guarantee an acceptable welfare mainly for juvenile stockings.

352 The need to ensure a sufficient vital volumes to fish stocks able to comply with their U_{welf} , has
353 driven the BGF design process towards a partial shelter to incoming waves provided by the
354 platform immersed walls, and to the provision of a deep volume by the relevant depth of cage
355 nets. In view of the future offshore aquaculture development, the present study supports the
356 definition of the operational limits for offshore cages taking into the due account the fish
357 endurance. Although an early author (Turner, 2000) pointed out the issue of fish surviving
358 capability in offshore conditions, the current technological rush to offshore aquaculture has
359 only so far been driven by the engineering challenges aimed at extending the capability of
360 farming structures to operate and survive in extreme sea states. The fish stocks have received
361 scant attention, even though they are sentient vertebrate animals that must be ensured of
362 acceptable (from the fish point of view) farming conditions (see Council of Europe (2006), and
363 Toni et al. (2019) for a review of EU Directives and recommendations on fish welfare). In
364 high-energy offshore sites, production facilities should be able to offer an adequate shelter to
365 fish stocks, either by defensive structures or by deeper cages, even when requesting an elevated
366 degree of automation for husbandry practice, compared to common offshore cages.

367 The recent MPP design developments, supported by several FP7 (MERMAID, TROPOS and
368 H2Ocean) and H2020 initiatives (Space@Sea and The Blue Growth Farm) have explored the
369 possibility of joining aquaculture to offshore space and renewable exploitation. The challenges
370 posed by the associated development of marine renewables, based on high-energy sites, and
371 aquaculture, so far operating successfully in mild conditions, have not been sufficiently
372 addressed since the very early conceptual elaborations, not adequately having taken into
373 account the limits of fish welfare in exposed sites. On the basis of this study, the future MPPs

374 design will be oriented towards structures able to support deep cages, either from a dynamic
375 point of view than as operational needs.

376 The present study aims to contribute to a welfare-based design of MPPs and, more generally,
377 of offshore aquaculture installations. At the same time, it offers a rationale for allocating
378 offshore areas suitable for aquaculture, on the basis of specific wave climate knowledge, and
379 when the fish endurance limits of a relevant number of species will be available in the future.

380 **Conclusion**

381 During the process of siting of MPP designed to support fish farming in offshore areas, the
382 fish endurance to extreme sea states should not be overlooked and, as for engineering
383 standards for offshore infrastructures, a criterion to set the limiting sea state conditions
384 leading to acceptable fish welfare should be included in the design process, both to comply
385 with the legal and ethical farming requirements and to provide an adequate production
386 environment.

387 The orbital movements generated by waves are deemed capable of affecting fish welfare, in
388 analogy with the unidirectional currents. The present study provides a new perspective on
389 fish welfare, based on the environmental energy due to the orbital water motion, in offshore
390 areas where wave movements dominate the hydraulic environment.

391 The acceptable limits of wave motion at various depths under different sea states are
392 presented, for seabream, seabass and Atlantic salmon. For these species, the limiting wave
393 orbital speed is set at a safety value with respect to their U_{crit} , as a threshold criterion for
394 welfare in offshore cage farming.

395 **Acknowledgements**

396 This study has been produced in the framework of the Blue Growth Farm project

397 (<http://www.thebluegrowthfarm.eu/>), which has received funding from the European Union's
398 Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement number 774426.
399 The content of the work does not reflect the opinion of the European Commission but only
400 the views of the authors, including errors or omissions. The European Commission is also not
401 liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

402 **References**

- 403 Ashley, P.J., 2007. Fish welfare: current issues in aquaculture. *Applied Animal Behaviour*
404 *Science* 104, 199–235.
- 405 Barasan F., Ozbilgin H., Ozbilgin Y.D., 2007. Comparison of the swimming performance of
406 farmed and wild gilthead seabream, *Sparus aurata*. *Aquaculture Research* 38, 452–456.
- 407 Bellwood, D.R., Wainwright, P.C., 2001. Locomotion in labrid fishes: implications for
408 habitat use and cross-shelf biogeography on the Great Barrier Reef. *Coral Reefs* 20,
409 139–150.
- 410 Blake, R.W., 1983. *Fish locomotion*. New York, Cambridge University Press.
- 411 Blanchet, S., Loot, G., Dodson, J.J., 2008. Competition, predation and flow rate as mediators
412 of direct and indirect effects in a stream food chain. *Oecologia* 157, 93–104.
- 413 Boccotti, P., 2004. *Idraulica marittima*. Turin, UTET.
- 414 Bodkin, J.L., VanBlaricom, G.R., Jameson, R., J., 1987. Mortalities of kelp-forest fish
415 associated with large oceanic waves off Central California, 1982–1983. *Environmental*
416 *Biology of Fishes* 18(1), 73–76.

417 Booth, R., Scott McKinley, R., Økland, F., & Sisak, M. 1997. In situ measurement of
418 swimming performance of wild Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) using radio transmitted
419 electromyogram signals. *Aquatic Living Resources* 10(4), 213–219.

420 Brett, J. R., 1964. The respiratory metabolism and swimming performance of young sockeye
421 salmon. *Journal of the Fisheries Research Board of Canada* 21, 1183–1226.

422 Carbonara P., Scolamacchia M., Spedicato M.T., Lembo G., Zupa W., McKinley R.S., 2006.
423 Swimming performances as a well-being indicator of reared seabass *Dicentrarchus*
424 *labrax* (Linnaeus, 1758). Preliminary results. *Biol. Mar. Mediterr.* 13 (1), 488-491.

425 Castro, V., Grisdale-Helland, B., Helland, S.J., Torgersen, J., Kristensen T. et al. 2013.
426 Cardiac molecular-acclimation mechanisms in response to swimming-induced exercise
427 in Atlantic salmon. *PLoS ONE* 8(1), e55056.

428 Cheal, A.J., Coleman, G., Delean, S., Miller, I., Osbourne, K., Sweatman, H., 2002.
429 Responses of coral and fish assemblages to a severe but short-lived tropical cyclone on
430 the Great Barrier Reef, Australia. *Coral Reefs* 21, 131–142.

431 Code of Conduct for European Aquaculture, 2008. Federation of European Aquaculture
432 Producers (FEAP).

433 Connell, J.H., 1997. Disturbance and recovery of coral assemblages. *Coral Reefs* 16, 101–
434 113.

435 Council of Europe 2006. Standing Committee of the European Convention for the Protection
436 of Animals kept for farming purposes recommendation concerning farmed fish.

437 Davison, W., 1997. The effects of exercise training on teleost fish, a review of recent
438 literature. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology*, part A 117, 67–75.

- 439 Dempster, T., Korsøen, O., Folkedal, O., Juell, J. E., & Oppedal, F., 2009. Submergence of
440 Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.) in commercial scale sea-cages: A potential short-term
441 solution to poor surface conditions. *Aquaculture* 288, 254–263.
- 442 Denny, M.W., Gaylord, B., 2002. The mechanics of wave-swept algae. *Journal of*
443 *Experimental Biology* 205, 1355–1362.
- 444 Ebeling, A.W., Hixon, M.A., 1991. Tropical and temperate reef fishes: comparison of
445 community structures. In: Sale, P.F. (ed) *The ecology of fishes on coral reefs*, pp. 509–
446 563. Sydney, Academic Press.
- 447 Farlinger, S., Beamish, F.W., 1977. Effects of time and velocity increments on the critical
448 swimming speed of largemouth bass (*Micropterus salmoides*). *Transactions of the*
449 *American Fisheries Society* 106, 436–439.
- 450 Fischer, P., Eckmann, R., 1997. Spatial distribution of littoral fish species in a large European
451 lake, Lake Constance. *Ger Arch Hydrobiol* 140, 91–116.
- 452 Fisher, R., 2005. Swimming speeds of larval coral reef fishes: impacts on self- recruitment
453 and dispersal. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 285, 223–232.
- 454 Fisher, R., Bellwood, D.R., 2003. Undisturbed swimming behaviour and nocturnal activity of
455 coral reef fish larvae. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 263, 177–188.
- 456 Fisher, R., Wilson, S.K., 2004. Maximum sustainable swimming speeds of nine species of
457 late stage larval reef fishes. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 312,
458 171–186.
- 459 Follet, W.T., 1970. Benthic fishes cast ashore by giant waves near Pt. Joe, Monterey County,
460 California. *Proc. California Academy of Sciences* 224, 1251–1254.

461 Fulton, C. J., 2005. Wave energy and the role of swimming in reef fish ecology. PhD thesis,
462 James Cook University, Australia.

463 Fulton, C.J., Bellwood, D.R., Wainwright, P.C., 2001. The relationship between swimming
464 ability and habitat use in wrasses (Labridae). *Marine Biology* 139, 25–33.

465 Fulton, C.J., Bellwood, D.R., 2004. Wave exposure, swimming performance, and the structure
466 of tropical and temperate reef fish assemblages. *Marine Biology* 144, 429–437.

467 Gabel, F., Stoll, S., Fischer, P., Pusch M.T., Garcia, X.F., 2011. Waves affect predator-prey
468 interactions between fish and benthic invertebrates. *Oecologia* 165(1), 101–109.

469 Gallagher, P. E., Thorarensen, H., Kiessling, A., Farrell, A. P., 2001. Effects of high
470 intensity exercise training on cardiovascular function, oxygen uptake, internal oxygen
471 transport and osmotic balance in chinook salmon (*Oncorhynchus tshawytscha*) during
472 critical speed swimming. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 204, 2861–2872.

473 Hammer, C., 1995. Fatigue and exercise tests in fish. *Comparative Biochemistry and*
474 *Physiology* 112A, 1–20.

475 Hartwell, S.I., Otto, R.G., 1991. Critical swimming capacity of the Atlantic Silverside,
476 *Menidia menidia* L. *Estuaries* 14, 218–221.

477 Hasselmann, K., Barnett, T.P., Carlson, H., Cartwright, D.E., Enke, K., Ewing, J.A.,
478 Gienapp, H., Hasselmann, D.E., Krusemann, P., Meerburg, A., Muller, P., Olbers, D.J.,
479 Richter, K., Sell, W. & Walden, H., 1973. Measurements of Wind-Wave Growth and
480 Swell Decay during the Joint North Sea Wave Project (JONSWAP). Hamburg,
481 Deutsches Hydrographisches Institut. *Reihe A*(8), 12.

482 Hawkins, D.K., Quinn, T.P., 1996. Critical swimming velocity and associated morphology of
483 juvenile coastal cutthroat trout (*Onchorhynchus clarkii*), steelhead trout (*Oncorhynchus*
484 *mykiss*), and their hybrids. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 53,
485 1487–1496.

486 Herskin, J., Steffensen, J.F., 1998. Energy savings in sea bass swimming in a school:
487 measurements of tail beat frequency and oxygen consumption at different swimming
488 speeds. *Journal of Fish Biology* 53, 366–376.

489 Hughes, T.P., Connell, J.H., 1999. Multiple stressors on coral reefs: a long-term perspective.
490 *Limnology and Oceanography* 44, 932–940.

491 Huntingford, F.A., 2010. Exercise and welfare. In: *Proceedings of the FitFish workshop on*
492 *the swimming physiology of fish*, p. 29. Barcelona, 2–3 July 2010.

493 Hvas, M., Folkedal, O., Solstorm, D., Vågseth, T., Fosse, J. O., Gansel, L. C., Oppedal, F.,
494 2017. Assessing swimming capacity and schooling behaviour in farmed Atlantic
495 salmon *Salmo salar* with experimental push-cages. *Aquaculture* 473, 423-429.

496 Johansson, D., Juell, J.E., Oppedal, F., Stiansen, J. E., Ruohonen, K., 2007. The influence of
497 the pycnocline and cage resistance on current flow, oxygen flux and swimming
498 behaviour of Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.) in production cages. *Aquaculture* 265,
499 271–287.

500 Johansson, D., Laursen, F., Fernö, A., Fosseidengen, J.E., Klebert, P., Stien, L.H., Vågseth,
501 T., Oppedal, F., 2014. The interaction between water currents and salmon swimming
502 behaviour in sea cages. *PLoS One* 9, e97635.

503 Jones, D.R., Kiceniuk, J.W., Bamford, O.S., 1974. Evaluation of the swimming performance
504 of several fish species from Mackenzie River. *Journal of Fisheries Research Board of*
505 *Canada* 31, 1641–1647.

506 Jordaan, A., 2010. Fish assemblages spatially structure along a multi-scale wave energy
507 gradient. *Environmental Biology of Fishes* 87, 13–24.

508 Kolok, A.S., 1991. Photoperiod alters the critical swimming speed of juvenile largemouth
509 bass, *Micropterus salmoides*, acclimated to cold water. *Copeia*, 1085–1090.

510 Lassig, B.R., 1982. The minor role of large transient fishes in structuring small-scale coral
511 patch reef assemblages. PhD Thesis, Macquarie University, Australia.

512 Lassig, B.R., 1983. The effects of a cyclonic storm on a coral reef fish assemblages.
513 *Environmental Biology of Fishes* 9, 55–63.

514 Luna-Acosta, A., Lefrancois, C., Millot, S., Chatain, B., Bégout, M.L., 2011. Physiological
515 response in different strains of sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*): swimming and aerobic
516 metabolic capacities. *Aquaculture* 317, 162–167.

517 Lowe, C.G., 1996. Kinematics and critical swimming speed of juvenile scalloped
518 hammerhead sharks. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 199, 2605–2610.

519 Mosetti, F. 1979. *Fondamenti di Oceanologia e Idrologia*. Turin, UTET.

520 Myrick, C.A., Cech, J.J., 2000. Swimming performance of four California stream fishes:
521 temperature effects. *Environmental Biology of Fishes* 58, 289–295.

522 Oppedal, F., Dempster, T., Stien, L., 2011. Environmental drivers of Atlantic salmon
523 behaviour in sea-cages: a review. *Aquaculture* 311, 1–18.

524 Palstra, A. P., Planas, J.V., 2011. Fish under exercise. *Fish physiology and biochemistry*
525 37(2), 259–272.

526 Palstra, A.P., Planas, J.V., Takle, H., Thorarensen, H., 2015. The implementation of
527 swimming exercise in aquaculture to optimise production. *Aquaculture Europe* 40(1),
528 20–22.

529 Plaut, I., 2000. Effects of fin size on swimming performance, swimming behaviour and
530 routine activity of zebrafish *Danio rerio*. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 203, 813–
531 820.

532 Plaut, I., 2001. Critical swimming speed: its ecological relevance. *Comparative Biochemistry*
533 *and Physiology Part A: Molecular & Integrative Physiology* 131, 41–50.

534 Reidy, S.P., Kerr, S.R., Nelson, J.A., 2000. Aerobic and anaerobic swimming performance of
535 individual Atlantic cod. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 203, 347–357.

536 Remen, M., Solstorm, F., Bui, S., Klebert, P., Vågseth, T., Solstorm, D., Hvas, M., Oppedal,
537 F., 2016. Critical swimming speed in groups of Atlantic salmon *Salmo salar*.
538 *Aquaculture Environment Interactions* 8, 659–664.

539 Segner, H., Reiser, S., Ruane, N., Rösch, R., Steinhagen, D., Vehanen, T., 2019. *Welfare of*
540 *fishes in aquaculture*. FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Circular No. 1189. Budapest,
541 FAO.

542 Solstorm, F., Solstorm, D., Oppedal, F., Fernö, A., Kenneth Fraser, T.W., Olsen R.E., 2015.
543 Fast water currents reduce production performance of post-smolt Atlantic salmon
544 *Salmo salar*. *Aquaculture Environment Interactions* 7, 125–134.

545 Stien, L.H., Dempster, T., Bui, S., Glaropoulos, A., Fosseidengen, J.K., Wright, D. W.,
546 Oppedal, F. 2016. ‘Snorkel’ sea lice barrier technology reduces sea lice loads on
547 harvest-sized Atlantic salmon with minimal welfare impacts. *Aquaculture* 458, 29–37.

548 Stoll, S., Fischer, P., 2010. Three different patterns of how low-intensity waves can affect the
549 energy budget of littoral fish: a mesocosm study. *Oecologia*. Toni, M., Manciocco, A.,
550 Angiulli, E., Alleva, E., Cioni, C., Malavasi, S., 2019. Review: Assessing fish welfare
551 in research and aquaculture, with a focus on European directives. *Animal* 13(1), 161–
552 170.

553 Thorstad, E.B., Finstad, B., Økland, F., McKinley, R.S., Booth, R.K. 1997. Endurance of
554 farmed and sea-ranched Atlantic salmon *Salmo salar* L. at spawning. *Aquaculture*
555 *Research* 28, 635–640.

556 Turner, R., 2000. Offshore mariculture: Site evaluation. In: Muir J. (ed.), Basurco B. (ed.).
557 *Mediterranean offshore mariculture*. Zaragoza, CIHEAM, 2000, 141–157. (Options
558 Méditerranéennes: Série B. Etudes et Recherches; no. 30.)

559 Videler, J.J., 1993. *Fish swimming*. London, Chapman & Hall.

560 Webb, P.W., 1984. Body form, locomotion and foraging in aquatic vertebrates. *American*
561 *Zoologist* 24, 107–120.

562 Webb, P.W., 2002. Control of posture, depth and swimming trajectories of fishes. *Integrative*
563 *and Comparative Biology* 42, 94–101.

564 Weihs, D., 1989. Design features and mechanics of axial locomotion in fish. *American*
565 *Zoologist* 29, 151–160.

- 566 Weihs, D., 1993. Stability of aquatic animal locomotion. *Contemporary Mathematics* 141,
567 443–461.
- 568 Williams, I.V., Brett, J.R., 1987. Critical swimming speed of Fraser and Thompson River
569 pink salmon (*Oncorhynchus gorbuscha*). *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic*
570 *Sciences* 44, 348–356.
- 571 Wilson, R.W., Egginton, S., 1994. Assessment of maximum sustainable swimming
572 performance in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *Journal of Experimental Biology*
573 192, 299–305.
- 574 Wood, C.M., 1991. Acid-base and ion balance, metabolism, and their interactions, after
575 exhaustive exercise in fish. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 160, 285–3.
- 576 Zanuttigh, B., Angelelli, E., Kortenhaus, A., Koca, K., Krontira, Y., Koundouri, P., 2016.
577 Methodology for multi-criteria design of multi-use off-shore platforms for marine
578 renewable energy harvesting. *Renewable Energy*, 85, 1271–1289.